

Applying Integration Analysis for Typological Identification of Urban Forests in Zagreb

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Abstract: As key components of green infrastructure, urban forests support biodiversity, improve environmental quality and residents' well-being. They contribute to cultural, historic and aesthetic values of cities and function as important open public spaces for rest and recreation. This study examines the potential of using space syntax, a quantitative method for analysing spatial configuration, as a tool for assessing inherent spatial characteristics of urban forest's configurations in Zagreb, Croatia. Together with comparisons to protected natural and cultural heritage areas, these findings provide a basis for developing an analytical framework for typological identification of urban forests. These preliminary results indicate correlation of high accessibility and significant cultural and historical value. By combining urban morphology, geospatial analysis and heritage protection, this research demonstrates how quantitative metrics can inform evidence-based planning strategies with comparative categorisation of spatial urban systems that promote sustainability, biodiversity and cultural values.

Keywords: urban forests; space syntax; spatial configuration; Zagreb; open public space.

1 Introduction

Urban forests are natural public spaces that provide ecosystem services, contribute to residents' well-being and shape local identity (Knez et al. 2018, Pinto et al. 2022). They have been well explored in forestry and environmental sciences, particularly in terms of their ecological functions. Building on this foundation, an interdisciplinary research approach is required for planning them and their surroundings, as the relationship of urban forests and the urban fabric significantly shapes their use and perception. Therefore, the space syntax approach is used as an analytical basis for exploring urban forest integration at city level which can connect multiple perspectives and fields in planning.

Complex spatial distribution of urban forests in Zagreb is defined by the city's geographical position and topological configuration. Medvednica mountain acts as a major ecological and morphological anchor from which vegetation extends into the urban area in the form of linear corridors (Gašparović and Sopina 2018). In such a complex urban landscape, the space syntax methods can inform on differences and similarities of urban forests based on their integration and accessibility. Revealed patterns support the development of urban forests categorisation that guides towards context-sensitive planning strategies. The aim of this study is to form an analytical quantitative

framework for typological identification of urban forests within the Zagreb spatial scope where 23 urban forests were compared. This framework answers the questions: How accessible are urban forests within Zagreb spatial configuration? What differences and similarities can be identified among Zagreb's urban forests in terms of spatial integration?

This paper presents preliminary results which are part of the first author's doctoral research. It is a step towards developing a multidisciplinary framework for urban forest research that employs analytical tools used in urban planning and landscape architecture.

2 Materials and methods

Space syntax is a theory and method for analysing spatial relationships in the built environment that originated in the 1970s by Bill Hillier and his colleagues at The Bartlett School of Architecture, University College London (UCL). Its foundation comes primarily from mathematics, specifically graph theory. It is used for observing how networks of space relate to functional patterns (e.g. vehicle and pedestrian movement) offering insight on how cities are constituted spatially as an effect of social, economic and cognitive factors (van Nes and Yamu 2018). A key point to highlight is that space syntax measures how every public space in a built environment relates to all other public spaces with values such as syntactic integration (to-movement) and choice (through-movement): "On the one hand, it measures the to-movement potential, or closeness, of each street segment with respect to all others. On the other hand, it measures the through-movement potential, or betweenness, of each street segment with respect to all others. The street network's to- and through-movement potentials represent various accessibility potentials." (van Nes and Yamu 2018, 7).

This research was developed using the existing syntactical (axial and segment) models of the city of Zagreb, developed in 2016 at UCL (Zaninović et al. 2018). These models are based on the axial map which represents the city's spatial configuration as a network of streets and open spaces composed of the longest and fewest straight lines. Axial lines capture visual corridors and routes of physical accessibility and include all main urban public spaces such as streets, squares and parks. Other used geodata includes protected natural areas, protected complexes of immovable cultural property and Zagreb Orthophoto imagery as background provided by the city municipality of Zagreb. *QGIS* (QGIS Development Team 2024) and *DepthMapX* (DepthMapX Development Team 2020)

programmes were used to support data processing and analyses.

Compared urban forests are defined by polygons and selected according to one of the following criteria: C1) protected as a monument of landscape architecture at national level (1), C2) proposed by the General Urban Plan (GUP) of the City of Zagreb for protection at national level as park-forest (8) or C3) protected at local level by GUP as city park-forests (14). Within the axial and segment models, internal and immediate external streets were selected to represent each urban forest. Three space syntax indicators were considered: Axial Integration (Int), Normalized Angular Integration (NaInt Rn) and Normalized Angular Choice (NaCh Rn).

Integration measures topological accessibility of spaces within the network, indicating how easily each segment can be reached from all others while Normalized Angular Integration measures global (city level) accessibility using angular distance. Normalized Angular Choice measures the through-movement potential of spaces based on angular shortest paths across the entire system (city level) (Hillier et al. 2012). To assess spatial characteristics and enable comparison, the difference between maximum and mean values (Max–Mean) was calculated for each urban forest. Space syntax metrics were then visualized and overlapped with areas protected as immovable cultural property, specifically cultural and historical complexes. Subsequent analysis explored correlations between space syntax metrics and heritage protection.

3 Results

Urban forests were ranked based on three syntactic indicators: Integration (Int), Normalized Angular Integration (NaInt Rn) and Normalized Angular Choice (NaCh Rn). A comparative analysis of these indicators revealed certain regularities in the distribution of urban forests within the resulting ranking.

The results show that certain urban forests exhibit a high degree of correspondence across all three indicators. Such correspondence suggests a ‘unified’ spatial structure in which different measures of syntactic hierarchy are mutually aligned. In contrast, for some urban forests, no clear correlation among the indicators was observed, suggesting a ‘fragmented’ spatial system. Furthermore, a group of ‘hybrid’ spatial systems of urban forests was identified in which partial correspondence is present, meaning that two indicators align while the third deviates.

Figure 1 shows the visualization of space syntax metrics in QGIS, enabling data interpretation of urban forest relations within urban fabric. Each urban forest is assigned a color corresponding to the magnitude of its values (ranking) according to three indicators (Int Max–Mean, NaInt Rn Max–Mean and NaCh Rn Max–Mean).

In order to enable subsequent comparative analysis, urban forests were categorized based on several criteria, including area, level of nature and cultural heritage protection, centrality within the city and spatial logic with syntactical metrics (Table 1, Figure 2).

Figure 1. Graduated view of urban forests based on Int Max–Mean, NaInt Rn Max–Mean and NaCh Rn Max–Mean.

Figure 2. Syntactical model of Zagreb with protected cultural heritage complexes (black outline) and urban forest types (unified - blue, fragmented - red, hybrid - magenta).

4 Discussion

Described quantitative analyses combined with qualitative characteristics of nature and cultural heritage protection areas in Zagreb provide a framework for categorising urban forests applying space syntax integration measures. Research was conducted in the context of Zagreb case study since its spatial configuration is located on slopes of Nature Park Medvednica with numerous forested areas. Since the criteria (C1, C2, C3) for urban forest selection was level of protection, their distribution across the city is relatively uneven with the majority situated north of the city center or in the northeastern parts (Figure 1). The selected sample of these 23 urban forests in Zagreb

Table 1. Categorisation of urban forests in urban planning based on various factors.

No	Urban Forest	Area ¹ (ha)	Nature Protection ²	Cultural Heritage Protection ³	Centrality ⁴	Spatial Logic ⁵
1	Podsused	8,26 (S)	+	++	/	unified
2	Lisičina	8,83 (S)	+	/	/	unified
3	Grmoščica	69,03 (M)	+	/	+	hybrid
4	Šestinski dol	8,42 (S)	+	+	++	fragmented
5	Vrhovec	29,73 (M)	++	++	+	fragmented
6	Zamorski breg	27,85 (M)	+	+	/	unified
7	Jenovac	53,15 (M)	++	++	/	hybrid
8	Pantovčak	121,88 (L)	++	++	/	fragmented
9	Prekrižje	14,81 (S)	++	++	/	unified
10	Kraljevec	47,18 (M)	++	++	/	hybrid
11	Zelengaj	32,91 (M)	++	++	++	hybrid
12	Tuškanac	55,71 (M)	++	++	++	unified
13	Remetski kamenjak	63,74 (M)	+	++	+	unified
14	Mirogoj	43,30 (M)	+	++	+	hybrid
15	Remete	98,14 (M)	+	++	/	unified
16	Maksimír	317,97 (L)	+++	++	++	hybrid
17	Dotrščina	327,06 (L)	+	++	++	hybrid
18	Miroševečina	109,98 (L)	+	/	/	hybrid
19	Dankovečina	181,88 (L)	+	+	/	hybrid
20	Granešina	29,51 (M)	+	+	+	fragmented
21	Oporovec	114,15 (L)	+	+	/	fragmented
22	Čulinečina	75,86 (M)	+	+	++	fragmented
23	Novoselčina	431,80 (L)	+	+	/	unified

¹ S: A < 10 ha, M: 10 ha > A < 100 ha, L: A > 100 ha; ² +++ protected at national level, ++ proposed for protection at national level, + protected at local level; ³ ++ protected as complex (part or whole), + protected complex in the immediate vicinity; ⁴ based on overlapping with the integration core (set of most integrated spaces in a spatial network): ++ = part of urban forest is within 20% of integration core, + = part of urban forest is within 40% integration core; ⁵ based on correlation between space syntax metrics (Int Max-Mean, NaInt Rn Max-Mean and NaCh Rn Max-Mean)

exhibits correlation with protected cultural heritage complexes, which may fully or partially overlap with them or occur in close proximity to them (Figure 2). The cluster of urban forests in the city centre is located entirely within the historic urban complex, as is the case in Podsused and Granešina. Maksimír is entirely protected as a landscaped green area, Dotrščina partly as a memorial complex and several urban forests in the far eastern part of the city are located in close proximity to rural complexes.

Urban forests that intersect with the 20% integration core are embedded in the most globally accessible areas of the city. Only a small number of forests exhibit this kind of integration (Šestinski dol, Zelengaj, Tuškanac, Maksimír, Dotrščina and Čulinečina), as expected and therefore the configurational analysis confirms and detects that the majority of urban forests in Zagreb are located in peripheral, topographically constrained areas. To further support, a single lowland urban forest (Čulinečina) located in the eastern part of the city shows a high level of integration, primarily due to its location adjacent to a major traffic corridor.

Zagreb is an exemplary case for exploring urban forest typologies due to its distinctive topographical setting between the Medvednica Nature Park and Sava River. From a total of 23 urban forests, this research established three distinctive types based on their syntactical properties of integration and choice (8 unified, 6 fragmented and 9 hybrid). A high concentration of interconnected urban forests of all three types is visible in the northern city centre. The western part is characterized by small, mutually distant urban forests where only two types are recognized. The eastern part contains numerous urban forests of large areas. The spatial distribution of certain types forms distinct zones extending in a north-south direction, which may reflect the configuration of foothills and linear corridors of Medvednica mountain (Gašparović and Sopina 2018).

Applied methodology enables result comparison with existing or future studies in urban areas with forests or other characteristics. This research ultimately seeks to deepen the understanding of urban forests as vital cultural infrastructure with ecological benefits, consequently supporting their sustainability, protection and

enhancement. Applying space syntax to analyse urban forests as open public spaces provides a comparative evaluation framework from an urban planning perspective that complements existing knowledge in forestry and environmental sciences.

5 Conclusions

This study establishes the foundation for a multidisciplinary approach in which urban forests aren't seen only as ecological and aesthetic spaces, but as spatially organised and socially active systems of cultural infrastructure. Because Zagreb has numerous urban forests, this research established types that provide insight into previously unrecognized inherent spatial relationships, revealing patterns that are not evident through conventional analysis.

Work conducted as part of this preliminary research identifies key directions for future typological studies applying integration and space syntax methods, including: systematic mapping of pedestrian paths within urban forests in the Zagreb syntactical model, application of space syntax metrics at the neighbourhood scale (R1500) and expanded comparative analysis that considers all types of cultural heritage in and around the urban forest perimeter. The proposed framework may be applicable to other cities, however that requires further testing and validation across different geographic and urban contexts, historical layers and urban morphologies. Future research would also benefit from possible collaborations among disciplines such as environmental psychology, urban ecology and heritage conservation.

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